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Review of commercial thermal energy storage in concentrated solar power plants: steam vs. molten salts

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1. Introduction

Carbon dioxide is responsible of over 60% of greenhouse gas (GHG) worldwide emissions [1-4], being the largest contributor factor to the climate change. As a result, this climate change has become a real threat and the uncertainty regarding energy supply in future decades will increase. Demand of energy has significantly increased recently due to the growth of worldwide population and the high industrialization [1]. This growth is mainly done in emerging countries where the needs of new generation plants are increasing significantly while in developed countries the growth of energy is related to replacement of end-of-life existing power plants. Renewable energy sources have been a key player to contribute to the world's CO₂ greenhouse gas emission reduction. Therefore, the final drive of renewable energy becomes essential both to the achievement of the objectives set out under the Energy and Climate Policy, and to ensure the future competitiveness of individual countries in a global energy market. Solar thermal, photovoltaic, wind, among others, are presented as key players of renewable energy technologies to achieve these objectives. By 2050 and beyond, a paradigm shift in terms of production, distribution and use of energy should be aligned with an overall energy consumption coming largely from renewable technologies. However, there is a strong mismatch between renewable energy supply and user demand.

Energy storage systems are designed to accumulate energy when production exceeds demand and to make it available at the user's request. They can help match energy supply and demand, exploit the variable production of renewable energy sources (e.g. wind and solar), increase the overall efficiency of the energy system and reduce CO₂ emissions [5]. An energy storage system can be described in terms of the following properties [6]:

- Capacity [MWh]: defines the energy stored in the system and depends on the storage process, the medium and the size of the system;
- Power [MW]: defines how fast the energy stored in the system can be charged and discharged;
- Efficiency [%]: is the ratio of the energy delivered during discharge to the energy needed to charge the storage system. It accounts for the energy loss during the storage period and the charging/discharging cycle;
- Charge and discharge time [h]: defines how much time is needed to charge/discharge the system;
- Cost [\$/kW or \$/kWh]: refers to either capacity (\$/kWh) or power (\$/kW) of the storage system. It can be referred as thermal or electric cost. Commonly, it includes the storage material itself, the heat exchanger for charging and discharging the system and the cost of the space and/or enclosure for the TES

Due to diversified demand profiles regarding to type, amount and power of needed energy, each energy storage system (electrical, thermal, mechanical or chemical) requires a specific, optimal solution regarding efficiency and economics.

Solar thermal electricity or concentrating solar power, commonly referred to as STE and CSP respectively, is unique among renewable energy generation sources because it can easily be coupled with thermal energy storage (TES) as well as conventional fuels, making it highly dispatchable [7]. It has been operating commercially at utility-scale since 1985 [8] and it generates electricity with a thermal power cycle similar to that used in conventional fuel-fired power plants. One advantage of this type of power cycle is that the thermal inertia in a STE system is generally sufficient to sustain energy production during cloudy periods [9]. Moreover, thermal energy can be stored for later use at a low cost relative to a backup system that uses batteries, having the ability to increase the capacity factor (ratio of the annual electricity generation to potential electricity generation) of a STE plant and thus increase its viability as a base load generator [10].

The easy integration of TES makes STE dispatchable and unique among all other renewable energy generating sources. From some years ago there is a very big increase of thermosolar power generation industry and its associated TES systems. They are crucial to ensure the success of the technology allowing dispatchability enough to supply energy when demanded.

Thermal energy storage has several advantages when compared to mechanical or chemical storage technologies. Generally, TES systems have lower capital costs as compared to other storage technologies [11-15], as well as very high operating efficiencies [16]. The Solar Two project demonstrated a thermal efficiency greater than 98% [17], which was defined as the ratio of the energy discharged to the energy stored in the TES system. The only losses are to the ambient through the insulation, they can be limited according to the amount of insulation used. This is the reason why very high thermal efficiencies mentioned above are reached.

A TES system mainly consists of three parts [7]: (i) the storage material, (ii) the heat transfer equipment, and (iii) the storage tank. The thermal energy storage material stores the thermal energy either in the form of sensible heat, latent heat of fusion or vaporization, or in the form of reversible chemical reactions. The heat transfer equipment supplies or extracts the heat from the storage material. The storage tank holds the storage material insulating the storage material from the surroundings. Depending on the type of storage, there are several requirements that must be considered to ensure optimal storage dynamics and longevity. These requirements are identified as [18]:

- High energy density in the storage material
- Good heat transfer between the heat transfer fluid (HTF) and the storage material
- Mechanical and chemical stability of the storage material
- Chemical compatibility between HTF, heat transfer equipment and storage material
- Complete reversibility for a large number of charging/discharging cycles
- Low cost
- Low thermal losses
- Low environmental impact

Thermal energy storage systems must be designed to meet certain criteria, which depend of the type, size and design of a STE plant. These criteria can be summarized as follows [18]:

- Nominal temperature and specific enthalpy drop in the load (charge and conversion side)
- Maximum load
- Operational strategy
- Integration into the plant

It can be easily understood that more than one storage technology is needed to meet different applications. Consequently, a broad spectrum of storage technologies, materials and methods are needed. The overall target in designing TES systems is the reduction of investment cost and the enhancement of efficiency and reliability. To achieve these objectives, material, design and system integration aspects have to be considered in equal measure.

The assessment of identification and selection of the optimal TES system is not only focused on the storage material. Other important components of the STE plant have also to be taking into account, as for example the storage tank or the heat exchanger. Devices and sub-components, which are needed for operation and integration, such as pumps, valves and control devices are also very relevant for the proper operation [19].

Two different thermal energy storage technologies are currently implemented in commercial solar thermal electricity plants: (i) the steam accumulator for direct steam generation plants, and (ii) the double tank of molten salts either for parabolic trough with thermal oil or the molten salt tower technology.

Abengoa is the only company whose portfolio includes different thermal energy storage concepts that have been already commercially proven. Based in this experience, the aim of this study is to confirm the need of having different storage technologies available in the market to better adapt the needs of demand/supply balance. The study compares both steam accumulator and molten salt technologies explaining the main advantages, disadvantages, challenges and particularities of each one. Firstly, a summary on the current status of the STE operating and under construction plants will be presented as well as commercial TES systems that are currently worldwide used. A cost comparison between the two concepts is presented in this paper in order to provide an assessment of the current commercial thermal energy storage systems used in STE plants.

Main CSP Technologies

The STE technology can be classified into parabolic trough, tower, linear Fresnel, and parabolic dish. According to the way they focus the sunrays and whether the position of the receiver, they can be classified as follows: parabolic trough and linear Fresnel systems where the mirror tracks the sun along one axis (line focus), and tower and dish systems where the mirror tracks the sun along two axes (point focus). The receiver is maintained fixed in linear Fresnel and tower systems, while is mobile in parabolic trough and dish systems.

In parabolic trough technology, the sun's energy is concentrated by a parabolically curved trough-shaped reflector onto a receiver tube running along the inner side of the collector [20]. The energy concentrated in the receiver tube heats a HTF, commonly synthetic oil, that flows through the tube along the trough collector and the heated HTF is then used to generate electricity in a conventional steam generator-turbine. Parabolic trough technology can also be integrated with existing coal-fired plants or combined cycles[---].

Solar power tower converts sunshine into electricity using many large sun-tracking mirrors, also called heliostats, by focusing the sunlight on a receiver located at the top of a tower [20]. The HTF that flows in the receiver, commonly molten salts or water/steam, is heated by these sunlight and then used in a conventional steam generator and turbine to produce electricity.

On the other hand, linear Fresnel technology [21] uses flat or slightly curved mirrors mounted on trackers on the ground that are configured to reflect sunlight onto a receiver tube fixed in space above the mirrors. A small parabolic mirror is sometimes added atop the receiver to further focus the sunlight.

Parabolic dish systems consist of a parabolic-shaped point focus concentrator in the form of a dish that reflects solar radiation onto a receiver mounted at the focal point [20]. These concentrators are mounted on a structure with a two-axis tracking system to follow the sun. The collected heat is typically used directly by a heat engine mounted on the receiver moving with the dish structure. Stirling and Brayton cycle engines are currently favored for power conversion.

[-----]

For each technology, various options exist for the heat transfer fluid (HTF), thermal energy storage (TES) and power cycle.

The STE plants that are currently operating and being constructed have been reviewed. Details of their solar collector configuration, solar field operating conditions, TES systems and cooling methods have been summarized in Table 1 for the two most mature technologies, trough and tower.

	Current trough	Current tower
Maturity	High, commercially proven	Medium, recently commercially proven
Key technology providers	Abengoa Solar, Sener Group, TSK-Flagsol, Acciona, ACS-Cobra,	Abengoa Solar, BrightSource Energy, Solar Reserve, eSolar, Torresol
Typical plant capacity [MWe]	100	50-100
Operating temperature of solar field [°C]	290-390	290-565
Plant peak efficiency [%]	14-20	23-35
Annual average conversion efficiency [%]	13-15	14-18
Collector concentration [suns]	70-80	>1000
Power block cycle	Superheated steam Rankine	Saturated steam Rankine Superheated steam Rankine
Power block fluid conditions	steam @380°C/100 bar	steam @540°C/100-160 bar
Power cycle efficiency [%]	37.7	41.6
Heat transfer fluid	Synthetic oil, water/steam (DSG), molten salt (demo), air (demo)	Water/steam (DSG), molten salt, air (demo)
Annual capacity factor [%]	20-25 without TES 40-53 with 6h TES	40-45 with 6-7.5h TES 65-80 with 12-15h TES
Storage system	Indirect 2-tank Molten Salt storage	Direct 2-tank Molten Salt storage, Steam Accumulator
Storage temperature range [°C]	293-393	290-565 for Molten Salt storage 120-330 for Steam Accumulators
Capital cost [US\$/kW] (*)	4700-7300 (without TES, OECD countries) 3100-4050 (without TES, non-OECD countries)	6400-10700 (with TES)
LCOE [US\$/kWh]	0.26-0.37 (without TES) 0.22-0.34 (with TES)	0.2-0.29 (with 6-7.5h TES) 0.17-0.24 (with 12-15h TES)
Cooling method	Wet	Wet, dry
Suitable for air cooling	Low to good	Good
Water requirement [m ³ /MWh]	3 (wet cooling) 0.4-1.7 (hybrid cooling) 0.3 (dry cooling)	1.8-2.8 (wet cooling) 0.3-1 (hybrid cooling) 0.3 (dry cooling)

(*) OECD: Organization of Economic Co-operation and Development

Table 1 Representative features of the trough and tower STE technologies for current and future STE plants [7, 12, 22]

Current status of the market:

Figure 1 to Figure 4 present the overview of the STE sector with the worldwide capacity depending on countries and type of used technology, for solar thermal plants that are both operational and under construction. The information has been obtained from project listings [23, 24] as well as from Abengoa internal sources. As of January 2016, the STE market has a total capacity of 7638 MWe worldwide, among which 4801 MWe are operational and 2837 MWe are under construction. Estimations also consider that there are other 8472 MWe under development, which brings an overview of the growing potential of the STE sector in the development of new future projects to come.

Figure 1 STE worldwide plant capacity (January 2016) [23, 24]

Spain, the world leader country in CSP, had a total operational capacity of 2304 MWe. USA follows Spain with a total capacity of 1893 MWe. Other countries like South Africa, Chile, India, China and a few Middle East countries have grown their interest to develop solar thermal power plants recently. Among these countries, South Africa and Chile are the most promising ones for future STE developments due to the great acceptance of this technology.

Figure 2 STE worldwide operational plant capacity (January 2016) [23, 24]

Figure 3 STE worldwide under construction plants capacity (January 2016) [23, 24]

Parabolic trough systems dominate the global market and are currently the most proven STE technology, being installed in around 81% of the STE plants in operation and around 48% which are under construction. Regarding solar tower systems, there are around 14% of the total STE plants operating worldwide, while this percentage raise up to 28% for the tower plants which are currently under construction. The increase in the number of solar tower projects in the recent years shows that this system has achieved a good level of maturity allowing scaling the technology up to hundreds of MW. Parabolic dishes are at their early demonstration stage while Linear Fresnel plants are currently making the transition to commercial applications. Figure 4 presents the STE worldwide operational capacity by country and used technology. Figure 5 presents the STE worldwide under construction capacity by country and technology.

Figure 4 STE worldwide capacity in operation by country and technology (January 2016) [23, 24]

Figure 5 STE worldwide capacity under construction presented by country and technology (January 2016) [23, 24]

Slightly above than one third of the installed CSP capacity uses thermal storage. More precisely, a 36% of the total STE installed capacity. With the maturity of molten salt and steam accumulator storage technologies, over 53% of the capacity under construction has energy storage. This percentage increases up to 83% not considering the 1 GW solar plant under construction in Oman. Only considering the tower and trough technology, up to 73% (up to 78% not considering the 1 GW solar plant under construction in Oman) of the under construction capacity uses thermal energy storage. The current thermal storage technology used in linear Fresnel plant is short-term pressurized steam storage (<1h) and molten salt for long-term storage, being this long-term storage under development [25]. Only a few linear Fresnel under construction plants uses molten salt TES systems. Figure 6 presents the STE capacity with and without storage depending on the used technology.

Figure 6 STE worldwide capacity categorized by technology and with/without storage (January 2016) [23, 24]

2. Thermal energy storage systems

Thermal energy storage can solve the mismatch between solar energy supply and electricity demand, providing a distinctive advantage to STE plants compared to other renewable energies, like wind or photovoltaic [18]. To date, electrical energy storage using batteries has not proven to be economically feasible for large capacities [11-15, 26] compared to other energy storage technologies like TES. In addition no problems of shortage with storage mediums like water or nitrate mixtures are foreseen as in the case of lithium batteries where big increases are foreseen within the next years [27].

Solar power plants with thermal energy storage systems can have several operational strategies depending on the daily variations of supply/demand profiles. TES storage systems can be integrated to perform the following functions [7, 28]:

- Mitigation of short fluctuations during transient weather conditions, e.g. cloudy periods. Those periods of inclement weather can force the turbine to be operated into a transient mode thus reducing the turbine efficiency due to start-up losses. Even if heat transfer fluids have some thermal inertia that could help the plant continue operating during short cloudy periods [29], experiences with large-scale facilities have shown that it may not be enough to prevent a turbine shut-down [30]. Small capacity storage systems could help to mitigate those short fluctuations of solar radiation.
- Shifting the generation period from peak hours of solar insolation to peak hours of power demand; thermal energy storage system can improve dispatchability by storing energy during off-peak hours and then discharging it during peak hours of demand [18].
- Extending the generation period when solar resource is not available, acting as baseload electricity generation and improving the annual capacity factor (requires larger solar field than a system without storage). This annual capacity factor can be defined as a performance parameter that compares net electricity delivered by the solar facility to the energy that could have produced under continuous full-power operation during a year. As solar resource is only available during some hours of the day, thermal energy storage systems can improve the capacity factor allowing operating the plant when no sun is available, and if large enough, operate for 24h.

2.1. Thermal energy storage concepts:

a) 2.1.1. Classification

Thermal energy storage concepts for high temperature solar power plants can be classified as active or passive systems [CCC]. An active system is mainly characterized by forced convection heat transfer into the storage material whose storage medium itself circulates through a heat exchanger. Active systems can be divided into direct or indirect systems.

Fig. 2. Scheme of classification of different storage systems according to the storage concept.

b) Active system

An active direct system uses the heat transfer fluid also as the storage medium. That means the material must have particularly characteristics in order to be a good heat transfer fluid and a good storage medium at the same time. The use of steam or molten salt as the HTF and storage material at the same time eliminates the need of costly heat exchangers. Steam or molten salts also allows the solar field to be operated at higher temperatures than current heat transfer fluids commonly used in parabolic trough oil plants, which are limited by the degradation temperature of synthetic oil. All these aspects allow reducing the TES system cost improving the performance of the plant and reducing the levelised cost of electricity (LCOE). In the case of molten salt and as per D. Kearney, it only makes sense from economic point of view to include thermal energy storage in solar facilities when using molten salt as heat transfer fluid [31,32].

Since the freezing point of currently used molten salts is considerably high, special attention has to be dedicated to freeze protection operation: the HTF is circulated through the solar field during the whole night, in order to maintain piping warm and avoid critical thermal gradients during start-up; if the HTF temperature falls below a certain value, an auxiliary heater is used to maintain the minimum value.

One of the active direct systems is the two tanks direct system, which consists in a storage system where the HTF is directly stored in a hot tank, in order to use it during cloudy periods or nights. The cooled HTF is pumped to the other tank, cold tank, where it remains waiting to be heated one more time [7]. Fig. XX shows the scheme of the plant Gemasolar, that uses molten salts (NaNO_3 and KNO_3) as HTF. Gemasolar is placed on Fuentes de Andalucía, near to Seville (Spain) and was built during 2008.

The advantages of the two tanks solar systems are: cold and heat storage materials are stored separately; low-risk approach; possibility to raise the solar field output temperature to 450/500°C (in trough plants), thereby increasing the Rankine cycle efficiency of the power block steam turbine to the 40% range (conventional plants have a lower efficiency) [6]; and the HTF temperature rise in the collector field can increase up to a factor of 2.5 compared to Solar Two experience (located in Daggett, CA, built in 1995 and decommissioned in 1999), reducing the physical size of the thermal storage system [6,7].

The disadvantages are very high cost of the material used as a HTF and storage material; high cost of the heat exchangers, the need of using two tanks instead of one; relatively small temperature difference between the hot and the cold fluid in the storage system; very high-risk of solidification of storage fluid, due to its relatively high freeze point (which increases the M&O costs); the high

temperature of both tanks drives to an increase of losses in the solar field; and the lowest cost TES design and operation does not correspond to the lowest cost of electricity (usually at night) [9].

Figure 7 Schematic flow diagram of a molten salt tower plant with 2-tank direct molten salt storage system [39]

In an active indirect system, a second medium is used for storing the thermal energy, meaning that the use of a heat exchanger is needed to transfer the energy from the heat transfer fluid that circulates in the solar field to the second medium that acts as the storage medium. Within the active indirect systems, it is possible to find the following technologies: (i) two tanks indirect systems and (ii) single tank system (also named thermocline system), the last one being a technology not commercially available to date and still under development. The advantages of a thermocline tank storage system are the reduction of storage tank number because this system only uses one tank, which means cost reduction. However, separation between the hot and cold HTF maintaining the thermal stratification and avoiding mixing requires complex procedures and thermomechanical design of the storage tank. Thermodynamically, it could be an inefficient power plant [30].

Figure 8 Schematic flow diagram of an oil-parabolic trough solar power plant with 2-tank indirect molten salt [35]

Fig. 5. Scheme of installation of a parabolic through power plant, with single-tank storage system [10].

c) **Passive system**

A passive system is mainly the dual medium storage system where the heat transfer fluid passes through the storage only for charging and discharging the storage medium. The HTF exchanges the energy to the storage medium during the charging phase and receives energy from the storage when discharging.

The main disadvantage of passive systems is that the HTF temperature decreases during discharging as the storage medium cools down. In addition, the heat transfer is rather low and usually there is no direct contact between the heat transfer fluid and the storage medium as the heat is transferred by a heat exchanger.

[Poner foto de Sistema pasivo]

There are many types of TES that could be applied for solar thermal power plants (e.g. sensible heat storage, latent heat storage, or thermochemical storage). However, to date, only two kinds of thermal energy storage have been applied in commercial STE plants: (i) molten salt and (ii) steam accumulator storage.

Molten salt storage is being used as an active indirect storage system using parabolic trough oil plants with a molten salt TES, and also as an active direct storage system using solar tower or central receiver systems with molten salt storage. In the case of steam accumulator storage, it is used in solar tower plants with Direct Steam Generation (DSG) like PS10, PS20 or Khi Solar One.

3.1 Thermal energy storage with molten salts

Molten salt is the most widespread heat transfer fluid for thermal energy storage in STE commercial applications due to its good thermal properties and reasonable cost. Nowadays, molten salts provide a thermal storage solution for the two most mature technologies available on the market (e.g. parabolic trough and tower) and could be used as direct and indirect storage depending of the selected plant philosophy. Both, trough and tower technologies, use double tank system as thermal storage configurations. This concept was successfully demonstrated in solar thermal demo plants [33]: CESA-1 (Spain) [EE, FF], Themis (France) [GG] and Abengoa's 8.1 MWhth storage capacity TES-MS (Spain) [XX, YY, ZZ,]. The 10 MWe Solar Two demonstration tower plant has also successfully demonstrated a 105 MWhth storage capacity TES system [30, AA, BB], being considered as the first pre-commercial scale 2-tank molten salt storage system. Solar Two operated from 1996 to 1999 and helped validate nitrate salt technology and reduce the technical and economic risks of molten salt technology [JJ].

All these demo plants have set the basis of commercial indirect or direct molten salt storage systems that are being installed worldwide. As commented previously thermocline tanks are still under development. Also, recent research and development activities have been on-going for the last years to use molten salts as HTF in parabolic trough plants.

The molten salt fluids commonly used are nitrate mixtures with a weight composition of 60%wt NaNO_3 and 40%wt KNO_3 , also called solar salt, which optimizes cost and thermal properties. These mixtures have been well known in solar industry for decades with wide bibliographic information and proven feasibility at both pilot and commercial scale [XX, YY, ZZ, AAA, 17, 30, ---]. Their prices are significantly stables in the market. However, corrosion phenomena should be taken into account regarding material compatibility due to impurity contents of these mixtures. Nevertheless, good performance with the most common materials used in the industry can be assured.

Other molten salt candidates to be used in solar thermal power plants are the Hitec salt, a ternary mixture of NaNO_2 , NaNO_3 , and KNO_3 , and the Hitec XL®, a ternary mixture of $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, NaNO_3 , and KNO_3 [DDD].

Classification	Acronym [Literature source]	Chemical salt composition
Binary system, common anion	Solar Salt [Bauer 2013a]	$\text{KNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_3$ (40-60 wt%)
Ternary additive, common anion	HitecXL [Siegel 2011]	$\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-KNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_3$ (42-43-15 wt%)
Ternary reciprocal	Hitec [Kirst 1940]	$\text{KNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_2\text{-NaNO}_3$ (53-40-7 wt%)

Due to the very strong demand, the research work for suitable molten salts mixtures for HTFs as well as thermal energy storage materials in solar thermal power plants [13,14] is very active recently. The studies on some inorganic salts used for thermal energy storage materials are available in several papers [15-19].

So far, several well-recognized commercial molten salts by eutectic mixtures of nitrates or nitrites have been used in concentrated solar power systems mainly for thermal storage purpose, but can also be used as HTF. A binary mixture, Solar Salt (60 wt.% NaNO_3 / 40 wt.% KNO_3) has been used as thermal storage material in the 10 MWe solar-II central receiver project in California [20-22], in the 2-tank direct system of the Archimede project in Italy [23], and the indirect thermal energy storage system for the Andasol plant in Spain [24,25]. Solar Salt has a thermal stability (below 600°C) and a relatively high melting point (220°C).

A new heat transfer fluid called Hitec, which is a ternary salt mixture of 53 wt.% KNO_3 / 7 wt.% NaNO_3 / 40 wt.% NaNO_2 , has been considered to replace the Solar Salt because of its low freezing point of 142°C [26]. Hitec is thermally stable at temperatures up to 454°C, and may be used at temperature up to 538°C for a short period [27].

A modified version, Hitec XL, is a mixture of 48 wt.% $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ / 7 wt.% NaNO_3 / 45 wt.% KNO_3 which melts at about 133°C and may be used at a temperature up to 500°C [28-43].

Table 1: Potential salt mixtures for HTF

	Solar Salt	Hitec	Hitec XL	(Sandia)	(Solar Millennium)
Composition (by weight)	60% NaNO_3 , 40% KNO_3	40% NaNO_2 , 7% NaNO_3 , 53% KNO_3	7% NaNO_2 , 45% KNO_3 , 48% $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	Quaternary (assumed %'s)	Quaternary nitrate/nitride (%'s unknown)
Freeze Point (°C)	220	142 ³	120	100	80
Upper Temp Limit (°C)	585 ²	450 - 538 ³	480 - 505 ⁴	475 - 500 ²	450

² Communication with R.W. Bradshaw at Sandia National Laboratory

³ Coastal Chemical Co., L.L.C

⁴ R. W. Bradshaw and N. P. Siegel, "MOLTEN NITRATE SALT DEVELOPMENT FOR THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE IN PARABOLIC TROUGH SOLAR POWER SYSTEMS", Energy Sustainability 2008, ES2008-54174, A.S.M.E.

Density (kg/m^3 @ 300°C)	1899	1860	1992	1992 ⁵	N/A
Specific Heat ($\text{J/kg} \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$ @ 300°C)	1495	1560	1447	1447 ⁵	N/A
Cost (\$/kg)	1.30 ⁶	1.93 ⁷	1.66 ⁷	2.15 ⁸	N/A
Cost (\$/°C/kJ)	0.87	1.24	1.15	1.49	N/A

⁵ Assumed values

⁶ Abencs (March, 2009)

⁷ Compiled from individual constituent prices from Univar (includes shipping) (March, 2009)

⁸ Compiled from individual constituent prices from SQM (includes shipping) with assumed %'s (June, 2009) and LiNO₃ created from LiCO₃.

Molten salts as storage medium has inherent risks due to high freezing points: 220°C for the solar salt, 120°C for Hitec and 130°C for Hitec XL®. Electric heat tracing systems and tank heaters are installed to minimize freezing risks. But these equipments involve high parasitic consumptions to maintain the salts hot enough even when the system is completely discharged.

In general, molten salt storage systems offer the possibility to supply electrical production at constant conditions thanks to maintain the storage material in different tanks when it is charged or discharged. It also becomes an interesting option as storage material because it has high energy density per specific volume and very high thermal inertia due to its high heat capacity and low thermal conductivity. Those thermal properties allow designing storage systems with minimum thermal losses that increases global efficiency of the plant. Compared to indirect molten salt storage, when it is used as direct storage medium, the inventory is minimized due to high temperature gradients between the hot and cold tank. Also intermediate equipment like the thermal oil to salt heat exchanger is removed.

3.1.1 Molten salt indirect thermal energy storage for oil parabolic trough technology

An oil parabolic trough solar plant consists of a large field of parabolic trough collectors, a heat transfer fluid/steam generation system, and a Rankine steam turbine/generator cycle. Optional thermal storage systems can also be added as it happens in the almost totality of the under-construction parabolic trough solar plants [34]. The double tank of molten salts represents an optimum system for this technology because it matches perfectly the thermal sensible behaviour of the thermal oil used currently. Thermal oil operation temperatures used to be between 290°C and 390°C approximately, being nitrate molten salts efficient and operable enough within this range of temperatures. The power cycle used with this system usually includes preheater, evaporator, superheater and reheater. Depending on the cycle design common efficiencies reached with this technology are around 37%.

Synthetic oil circulates through the collectors and heats the oil up to 393°C. The absorbed heat is exchanged in a steam generator in the power block, where the fluid is used to generate high-pressure superheated steam (100 bar, approx. 380°C) that is fed into a conventional reheat steam turbine to produce electricity. During summer months, these plants can typically operate around 10-12 hours a day at full-rated solar energy electric output. To achieve electric production during overcast or night time periods, thermal storage is integrated into the plant to allow solar energy to be stored and dispatched when power is required by the grid.

Using this configuration, the heat transfer fluid from the solar field is diverted through a heat exchanger that is used to charge the thermal storage system, heating molten salt from the cold storage up to 390°C and storing it in the hot salt storage tank. When the storage system is discharged, molten salt from the hot storage tank is sent back to the oil-to-salt heat exchanger and is used to heat cold HTF. The heated oil is then sent back to the power plant. The cooled salt is returned to the cold storage tank at temperature around 290°C.

Synthetic oil does not allow working at temperatures higher than 400°C due to thermal instability, which means that the vapor quality is moderate and consequently low Rankine cycle efficiencies are possible.

The used thermal energy storage system consists of the following elements: (i) nitrate salt inventory, (ii) hot and cold storage tanks, (iii) the oil-to-salt heat exchanger, and (iv) the molten salt circulation pumps.

Inorganic nitrate salt mixtures are the preferred storage medium due to a favourable combination of properties: specific heat of 1500 J/kgK, density of 1880 kg/m³, vapour pressure <0.01 Pa, very low chemical reactivity and cost (\$0.8 to \$1/kg). The main mixture used is a NaNO₃ and KNO₃, selected because of its low cost compared to other mixtures. For the design of molten salt storage systems, the working temperature is commonly at least 70°C above the freezing point.

The low vapour pressure of nitrate salts allows using vertical, field-erected tanks which are fabricated with carbon steel (commonly ASTM A-516 Gr.70 for both storage tanks) and use a self-supporting roof. Due to the high operating temperature of the tanks, the design needs special consideration to limit loadings and stress resulting from thermal effects such as thermal expansion and thermal cycling. Thicknesses of the walls will depend on the inner pressure and temperature, maximum water column of salts inside the tank, wind and seismic parameters, as well as maximum allowable stress and corrosion allowance of wall material under applicable standard codes. Walls and roof are insulated with mineral wool layers insulation. The insulation material must be able to insulate the tank from the surroundings and minimize losses. Figure 9 shows the different components of the 2-tank molten salt thermal energy storage used in Solar Two plant [36,37]. The foundation consists of different layers (moving up from the soil): (i) concrete slab, (ii) thermal foundation, (iii) foamglass insulation, (iv) insulating fire bricks, (v) steel plate liner, and (vi) sand. Also, a ringwall of insulating fire bricks along the perimeter supports the weight of the tank walls and roof.

Figure 9 Solar Two molten salt storage tank foundation [36]

Two tanks are used, one for the cold storage and the other one for the hot storage. Size and number of tanks will depend on the storage capacity and will vary with the salt inventory. Figure 10 shows part of the thermal energy storage tanks of the 280 MW Solana plant located in Arizona (USA) with 6 hours molten salt storage capacity.

Figure 10 View of the molten salt thermal energy storage tanks of Solana plant (280 MW) in USA (Source: Abengoa)

Inside the tanks are located the molten salt circulation pumps. These pumps are vertical design, where the pumps draw suction from the bottom of the tank while the motors are located above the tanks.

As an indirect storage, oil-to-salt heat exchangers are needed. During the charging phase, molten salts from the cold tank are pumped to the hot tank heating the molten salts by the HTF in a heat exchanger. On the other hand, during the discharging phase, molten salts from the hot tank are pumped to the cold tank and cooled down by the HTF, making the heat exchanger reversible depending the operation procedure. For that, among others, a conventional shell and tube design is used, where the high pressure fluid (oil) is placed on the tube side and the low pressure fluid (molten salt) is placed on the shell side. The tubes are rolled and seal welded to the tube-sheet in order to improve the reliability of the heat exchanger. Oil-to-salt heat exchangers are commonly fabricated with standard carbon steel (ASTM A-210) as the temperature operation or corrosion issues are not high enough to require using better materials as stainless steels. The oil-to-salt heat exchanger must accommodate a differential pressure between the HTF and the molten salts of around 15 to 20 bar [34].

These heat exchangers must be designed with small thermal approaches (in the range of 3°C to 10°C) in order to minimize the performance penalty of the Rankine cycle during the discharging. It is important to note that live steam temperature will be lower during the storage operation than during daytime, when steam is generated directly by the solar field. This leads to a slight decrease of power block efficiency overnight. Small thermal approaches also help to maintain a minimum oil temperature to return to the solar field during the charging. As commented previously, the double tank molten salt storage represents an optimum system for this technology because it matches perfectly the thermal sensible behaviour of the thermal oil used in current parabolic trough solar plants. Thanks to the utilisation of efficient heat exchangers the hysteresis between charge and discharge can be reduced to a few degrees (around 10°C). Thus the system is able to generate higher than 90% of the nominal conditions and being able to maintain constant conditions during the whole discharge phase. Figure 11 represents an estimation of the temperature profiles of

the heat transfer fluid and molten salts in an oil-to-salt heat exchanger of a parabolic trough solar plant with storage.

Figure 11 Temperature profiles of HTF and molten salts inside an oil-to-salt heat exchanger for a parabolic trough plant with indirect molten salt storage

From different commercial experiences with two-tank molten salt storage systems used with oil parabolic trough plants, the TES system is able to supply energy at constant conditions during the discharge. The high thermal inertia is also a benefit regarding thermal losses. In addition, there are no big concerns about corrosion of materials or degradation of salts.

On the other hand, it has been proven that the two-tank molten salt TES system needs significant time to change from charging to discharging conditions, not allowing the system as buffer storage. If compared with a DSG (trough or tower) plant, two extra heat exchangers (thermal oil to molten salts, and thermal oil to steam) in the case of indirect storage and one (molten salts to steam) in the case of direct storage are needed for these configurations. Nevertheless, it is one of the most cost-effective TES systems and the most used for parabolic trough technology with thermal oil as heat transfer fluid.

3.1.2 Molten salt direct thermal energy storage for tower technology

A solar tower plant consists of a large field of heliostats, a heat transfer fluid/steam generation system, and a Rankine steam turbine/generator cycle. As parabolic trough plants, optional thermal storage systems can also be added. This happens in the majority of the solar tower plants already in operation and under-construction. The direct double tank molten salt storage system is the most used, but not least, technology for this kind of plants that includes thermal energy storage. This point describes the 2-tank molten salt technology used as direct thermal energy storage system for tower technology.

Compared to the technology used in commercial parabolic trough plants with storage, thermal oil is substituted by molten salts. Up to date only nitrate mixtures are used in commercial plants, being able to withstand thermal and chemically temperatures up to 565°C. Above this temperature, nitrate mixtures are not proven to be thermally stable. From power cycle point of view, depending on the availability of cooling water at the site, the condenser in Rankine plant is cooled with either

wet or dry cooling towers. Wet-cooled plants are somewhat more efficient than dry ones, reaching efficiencies of around 43% versus 41%, respectively [38].

A molten-salt tower uses a tubular-type receiver mounted on top of a tower where the reflected solar energy from a heliostat field heats the molten salt receiver; molten salts are heated from 290°C to 565°C in the receiver and then enter into the hot thermal storage tank. Later, hot salts are pumped from the storage system to generate steam within a molten salt steam generator in the power block, where the molten salts are used to generate steam that is fed into a conventional reheat steam turbine to produce electricity. The cooled salt is returned through the thermal storage system to the receiver.

The thermal storage system buffers the molten salt steam generator from solar transients and also supplies energy during periods of no insolation, at night or on partly cloudy days. Since the salt remains in a single liquid phase throughout the process, and because of its relatively high heat capacity, it is stored in compact storage tanks. Compared to synthetic oil, molten salts allow working at higher temperatures, which means higher steam turbine inlet temperature and higher Rankine cycle efficiencies. The hot salt temperature of 565°C enables steam production at temperatures and pressures typical of those used in conventional subcritical Rankine plants, commonly superheated steam at 540°C and 130 bar and reheat steam conditions of 538°C and 30 bar approximately.

The used thermal energy storage system consists of the following elements: (i) nitrate salt inventory, (ii) hot and cold storage tanks, (iii) the oil-to-salt heat exchanger, and (iv) the molten salt circulation pumps.

The same molten salt mixtures are used in the molten salt tower case. Regarding the storage tanks, those have similar design of those employed at Solar Two and are designed under API-650 standards. Cold storage tanks are commonly fabricated with ASTM A-516 Gr.70 carbon steel while hot storage tanks are fabricated with stainless steel, mainly ASTM A-347H or ASTM A-321H. Due to the higher operating temperature for the hot storage tank, special design considerations are needed to limit loadings and stress resulting from thermal effects. That means better quality materials for the walls of the hot storage tanks. Walls, roof and foundations are based on the same concept for both parabolic trough and tower technology but each one with appropriate materials depending on the working temperatures. Tank foundations are also passively air-cooled. Inside the tanks are located the vertical design molten salt circulation pumps. Figure 12 shows the thermal energy storage tanks of the Solar Reserve 110 MW Crescent Dunes solar plant located in USA with 10 hours molten salt storage capacity.

Figure 12 View of the molten salt thermal energy storage tanks of Crescent Dunes plant (110 MW) in USA (Source: Solar Reserve)

For tower technology using molten salt as HTF and storage medium it seems compulsory to install a double tank of molten salts thermal storage system. The higher molten salt temperature gradient compared to the parabolic trough case allows storing more thermal energy with the same volume. On the other hand the energy exchange between the steam and the molten salts will be penalized, mainly during the evaporation phase. During this phase, the heat exchanged occurs from a lowering temperature heat source to a constant temperature sink (steam) which means loss of heat transfer area. Figure 13 shows an estimation of the temperature profiles of the steam and molten salts in the molten salt steam generator.

Figure 13 Temperature profiles of steam and molten salts inside the molten salt/steam generation system of a molten salt tower plant with 2-tank storage system

Molten salt steam generators consist generally of a shell and tube preheater, evaporator, superheater and reheater as well as steam drum. The high pressure fluid (steam) is placed on the tube side and the low pressure fluid (molten salt) is placed on the shell side. The tubes are rolled and seal welded to the tube-sheet in order to improve the reliability of the heat exchanger. Those equipments are fabricated in stainless steel, mainly ASTM A-347H, as the temperature operation or corrosion issues require such kind of materials. Table 2 lists an estimation of the molten salts and water/steam, inlet and outlet conditions.

Fluid	Temperature	Pressure (absolute)
Hot salt	565°C	12 bar
Cold salt	288°C	2.3 bar
Superheat steam	550°C	130 bar
Reheat steam	548°C	27 bar

Table 2 Estimation of molten salt and water/steam conditions for the steam generator in a molten salt tower

The charge is always done in the receiver located on the top of the tower not suffering any hysteresis between the charge and the discharge, thus the discharge is able to generate power at nominal conditions. The steam generator has to be designed with small thermal approaches (up to 10°C) in order to minimize the performance penalty of the Rankine cycle during the discharging.

The possible problems associated are mainly the same as with the parabolic trough technology with thermal oil but taking into account bigger temperatures which it is more restrictive from the point of view of corrosion and degradation temperatures. Cycle conditions used commercially up to date, can satisfy thermal and chemical performance of the nitrate salts. But improvements in temperature operation can lead with major problems related to corrosion issues in steel materials as well as degradation of the salts.

3.2 Thermal energy storage with steam accumulator

Molten salt is the most used thermal energy storage medium. However, water can also be used as storage medium in solar thermal power plants installing equipment called steam accumulators. Currently the best option is the use of a steam accumulator storage system for the thermal storage needs in for DSG power plants.

A steam accumulator is a direct storage system eliminating intermediate equipment like heat exchangers or steam generators. It is based on the Ruth accumulator system where the steam is directly stored at high pressure in accumulator tanks. Steam accumulators are not old fashioned relics from the past. Indeed, and far from it, these storage systems have been (and are being) used since many years in process industry and power generation plants to balance demand and generation of steam. In the Berlin island grid, a 50 MW power plant was operated with steam accumulators of 67 MWh storage capacity over a period of more than 60 years [40]. Nuclear, food manufacturing, biotechnology, hospital and industrial sterilization, and product testing rigs, among others, are other industries where steam accumulators are also used.

As described previously in this paper, one option for active direct thermal energy storage is the possibility of generating steam directly in the solar field and to use it as heat transfer fluid (HTF) and as storage medium.

3.2.1 Steam accumulator thermal energy storage for tower technology

Direct Steam Generation (DSG) is a commercial technological option in solar tower plants as it eliminates the need for intermediate heat transfer liquids while increasing overall plant efficiency

as well as reducing cost, increasing performance and becoming a more environmentally friendly technology. This is due, in part, to the fact that the water inside the receiver tubes absorbs the concentrated solar energy, and changes from liquid state into saturated steam and, subsequently, into superheated steam. The steam produced in the receiver is fed directly to the turbine without the need of any heat exchanger. Compared to the other commercial technologies available in the market, it eliminates the oil/water heat exchanger train or the molten salt/steam generator, incorporating water/steam separators. In addition, the limitations on the maximum trough solar field temperature imposed by the degradation of the thermal oil (up to 400 °C) or the limitation of the working temperature of nitrate molten salts in solar tower power plants (up to 565°C) disappear and, therefore, the technology allows access to more efficient high temperature power cycles. Furthermore, investment costs are reduced due to the elimination of intermediate equipment.

In order to solve the thermal degradation of synthetic oils and the freezing problems due to the utilization of molten salts in solar thermal power plants, a lot of research and development activities were done for the development of direct steam generation systems, and moreover, related to thermal energy storage.

In January 2016, only two commercial plants using steam accumulator thermal energy storage are in operation: PS10 and PS20, both located in Spain. They started commercial operation in 2007 and 2009, respectively, and they became not only the first two commercial solar towers in the world but also the starting point for the operation of the direct steam technology. First generation STE towers use saturated steam technology. Figure 14 represents schematically a flow diagram of PS10 and PS20 direct steam generation tower plant with steam accumulator thermal energy storage system.

Figure 14 Schematic flow diagram of a direct steam generation tower plant with steam accumulator thermal energy storage system [41]

The PS10 central receiver plant uses a 11 MWe saturated steam Rankine cycle with steam accumulator thermal energy storage. PS10 is composed by 624 heliostats (120 m² each) for a total reflective surface of around 75000 m². It is arranged in circular rows around the tower, concentrating solar radiation on a saturated steam cavity receiver placed on top of a 115 m tower. The storage system provides 20 MWh of storage capacity, equivalent to an effective operational capacity of 50 minutes at 50% turbine workload. The system is composed by 4 tanks that are

sequentially operated in relation to their charge status. During full load operation of the plant, part of steam produced by receiver at 250°C and 45 bar will be employed to charge the steam accumulators. When energy is needed to cover a transient period, energy from saturated water will be recovered at variable pressure, from 45 bar to minimum pressure allowed by the system to run the turbine. Figure 15 shows the steam accumulators at PS10.

Figure 15 Steam accumulators of PS10 plant (Source: Abengoa Solar)

The PS20 central receiver plant is composed of 1255 heliostats (120 m² each) and uses the same technology as PS10 but its power cycle reaches 20 MWe with an equivalent storage capacity of 50 minutes at 50% turbine workload using two steam accumulators that are discharged in sequence.

Steam produced in the receiver is sent to the turbine where it expands to produce mechanical work and electricity. The excess of steam is stored into the steam accumulators to be used later. PS10 and PS20 turbine operates at 250°C and 45 bar saturated steam conditions. At the exit of the turbogenerator unit steam is sent to a low pressure water-cooled condenser.

Second generation of STE direct steam towers uses superheated steam technology. Superheated steam technology uses a second receiver, whose main function is to re-heat the steam produced by the first receiver (evaporator), thus allowing reaching higher temperatures. The live steam, which feeds the turbine, can reach a temperature of 540 °C and 130 bars of pressure, increasing the efficiency of the power cycle by 30% compared to its forerunner PS20.

Khi Solar One, a 50 MWe tower, a second direct steam generation plant, uses steam accumulator thermal energy storage. It is located in Upington (South Africa), and it is currently in commissioning phase. It has a 205 m tower height and uses 4120 heliostats of 140 m² each. Khi Solar One has a storage capacity of around 2 hours using 19 steam accumulator tanks that allows storing the saturated steam generated in the evaporators, feeding the turbine and generating electricity even when there is no sun.

Figure 16 Steam accumulators of 50 MWe Khi Solar One plant (Source: Abengoa Solar)

Figure 17 shows a schematic flow diagram of the superheated direct steam tower Khi Solar One with steam accumulator thermal energy storage system.

Figure 17 Scheme of 50 MW Khi Solar One plant with steam accumulator TES system

3.2.2 Basic concept of steam accumulators

From design point of view, steam accumulators use sensible heat storage in pressurized saturated liquid water [42], where liquid and gas phases are in thermodynamic equilibrium. They profit from the high volumetric storage capacity of liquid water for sensible heat due to its high specific heat capacity [43]. Water is used as both storage medium and working fluid, so high discharge rates are possible, while the storage capacity is limited by the pressure vessel volume. The volume specific thermal energy density strongly depends on the variation of the saturation temperature resulting from the pressure drop during the discharge phase, which characteristic values are within the range of 20-30 kWh/m³ [43].

The steam accumulator consists of cylindrical or spherical pressure vessels partially filled with water, at a point between 50% and 90% full depending on the application. The accumulator system is charged with the surplus saturated steam produced at maximum pressure in the evaporator receiver. This surplus steam is injected into a mass of water stored under pressure by a distribution manifold, which is fitted with a series of steam injectors. The stored water content will increase in temperature, pressure and level until it finally achieves the saturation temperature for the pressure at which the plant is operating. If the steam accumulator is charged using saturated steam, there may be a small gain in water due to the radiation losses from the vessel. However, if the steam accumulator is charged using superheated steam there is a gradual loss of water due to evaporation.

During the discharge, steam is produced by lowering the pressure of the saturated liquid during discharge. When the pressure inside the tank drops, flash steam evaporation is generated at the rate demanded by the power block. The water level will fall during the discharging. If superheated steam is desired, a secondary storage system is needed to increase the temperature of the steam. Thus, it is possible to superheat the discharged saturated steam coming from one accumulator using a higher pressure saturated steam coming from a second accumulator, increasing the efficiency of the TES system as well as the cycle efficiency during the discharge.

Figure 18 Variable-pressure (Ruth's) steam accumulator [44]

Several criteria are important to ensure the steam accumulator works properly [45]:

- Enough water is needed inside the accumulator to provide the required amount of flash steam during the discharge period.
- Higher steam release rates will produce wet steam. The velocity and flow rate at which the flash steam is released from the water surface must be below a predetermined value. This

can be satisfied by ensuring the water surface area is large enough which, in turn, depends on the accumulator size.

- The evaporation capacity must be sufficient. It will depend on the pressure at which the water is stored when fully charged and the minimum pressure at which the accumulator will operate at the end of the discharge period. The larger the differential between these two pressures, the more flash steam will be produced.
- The steam accumulator inner pressure must be higher than the downstream pipeline pressure. This is necessary to create a pressure differential to allow the required flow from the accumulator to the rest of the plant.

3.2.3 Integration of steam accumulators in solar thermal power plants

During the start-up phase in a direct steam tower plant, the evaporator has to be preheated and producing a minimum steam mass flow rate in order to progressively start focusing the superheater while maintaining part of the solar field defocused. The negative impact of maintaining part of the solar field defocused can be reduced by using saturated steam coming from the steam accumulators. Furthermore, the energy remaining in the storage tanks after the end of the discharge process can also be used, if needed, to preheat lines and auxiliary systems reducing the start-up time for next operating day.

Steam accumulators are especially suited to meet the requirements for thermal energy storage in solar steam plants as for the PS10, PS20 or Khi Solar One cases, providing saturated or superheated steam at pressures well above 100 bar as in the case of Khi Solar One. However, steam accumulator shows a decline in pressure during the discharge process, not reaching nominal conditions within the turbine. On the other hand, fast reaction times and high discharge rates make steam accumulators a well-proven option for compensation of transients but also as a mid-term storage system to meet supply/demand curves when there is no radiation. Using the volume of components like separator drum or heat exchangers for storage of pressurized hot water is also a cost-effective approach to integrate and increase buffer storage capacity. The availability of steam accumulators also helps to reduce the requirements concerning reaction time and discharge rate for supplying stored energy over longer periods as well as to protect the components of power plants from the effects of transients.

3.2.4 Design of steam accumulator

Focusing on the design concept of steam accumulators used in superheated steam towers, the used thermal energy storage system consists of the following elements: (i) steam accumulator tank, (ii) foundations, and (iii) heat exchanger to superheat the saturated stream.

A steam accumulator consists of a steel pressure tank designed to resist high pressure and high temperature water/steam. Steam accumulators are generally cylindrical with elliptical ends, as this is structurally the most effective shape, being manufactured from boiler plate. In general, carbon steel is the most usual material used for the fabrication of steam accumulators. For the design of such equipment it is important to take thermal cycling into account in order that the material is able to withstand during the whole life of the plant without any failure. Limiting temperature gradients in the vessel walls is key to avoid thermomechanical stresses on steam accumulators. Even if the materials commonly used for this kind of equipment is very well-know (e.g. boilers), corrosion phenomena should be taken into account regarding water content impurities.

Steam accumulators may be of horizontal or vertical (standing) design but the main operational differences are characterised by their physical orientation. Horizontal accumulators have relatively shallow water level and large water surface area which are properties in direct contrast with those of vertical accumulators.

Regarding the sizing, it will depend on the needs of storage capacity. There are limitations regarding the maximum size of each steam accumulator, basically depending on the maximum operating pressure as well as transportation concerns to sites where solar plants are located. However, several units can be able to meet the total thermal energy storage capacity of the plant.

Crucial components of a steam accumulator are the internal nozzles. During the charging process, steam is injected into the water content. The incoming steam bubbles condense in the liquid and rise to the steam space increasing the pressure of the water/steam and leading to a higher saturation temperature. In large pressure vessels, and in order to use the entire storage content, water circulation is required. Ruths invented a method that consists of nozzles (see Figure 19) which turn the flow of steam upwards. Depending on the vessel position (horizontal or vertical), the nozzles are surrounded by a circulation pipe, wherein the water flows upwards [44] enabling circulation inside the accumulator. When correctly designed and operated, steam from a steam accumulator is always clean, and has a dryness fraction quite close to 1. The steam accumulator is designed with a large water surface and sufficient steam space in order to produce high quality steam. In the case of some vertical steam accumulators the steam space is enlarged to compensate for the smaller water surface. The vessel must have sufficient clearance above the water under fully charged conditions to give a reasonable surface area for steam release.

Figure 19 Charging nozzle with circulation pipe [44]

It is important to mention that the nozzle capacity reduces as the pressure in the vessel increases. Nozzle design and their placement (see Figure 20) inside the steam accumulator must be considered because at very low flow rates, the steam will tend to issue from the nozzles located closest to the steam inlet pipe. During the charging, steam (possibly with some bubbles), exits the nozzles at very high velocity, promoting turbulence and mixing the water mass. That means that orientation is key to avoid direct incidence to the walls. All the injectors should be installed as low as possible to ensure the maximum possible liquid head above them in order to maximise storage capacity.

Figure 20 Placement of nozzles in a steam accumulator [45]

From operation point of view and to increase discharge efficiencies with steam accumulators, two accumulators are discharged at the same time, one of them will produce saturated steam which will be superheated in a heat exchanger using the higher saturated steam leaving the second accumulator. The main function of the heat exchanger is to achieve the minimum allowable degree of superheated at inlet turbine.

One of the main advantages of steam accumulators is that the storage fluid is water, which eliminates the negative environmental impacts and reduces the uncertainty in the price of the storage medium. This advantage is seen when comparing with a molten salt TES based on nitrate salts. In addition, all of the equipments related to water/steam are entirely conventional and very well know and used in the industry. O&M costs are reduced significantly avoiding energy consumption of pumping the storage medium and the use of heat tracing systems which is not required neither in pipes nor tanks. Also fast reaction times and high discharge rates make steam accumulators a well-proven option for compensation of transients but also as a mid-term storage system to meet supply/demand curves when there is no radiation. The availability of steam accumulators also helps to protect the components of power plants from the effects of transients.

On the other hand, cost and complexity of tank manufacturing and the volume per energy stored are the main disadvantages. Conventional steam accumulator need high amount of steel being directly impacted on steel price in the market. Also the large specific volume in relation to the amount of energy stored is another disadvantage to consider. Regarding operation, steam accumulators discharge steam at lower pressure than the nominal pressure of the cycle, decreasing the efficiency of the TES system.

3. Cost analysis for TES comparison

The aim of this study is to perform a cost comparison between the two commercial thermal energy storage systems available in the market for STE plants. Detailed performance and cost analyses were conducted to evaluate the economic comparison of the concepts described in this paper. In the case of steam accumulators, they have been very well-proven for many years in the solar thermal industry. Regarding the molten salt two-tank storage system, this storage concept was successfully tested in the Solar Two project, and being applied for both parabolic trough and molten salt tower plants [46]. The paper presents the results of an economic evaluation, done for a Rankine cycle with different plant configurations, and storage concepts and sizes.

Three reference systems are chosen: (i) parabolic trough power plant with synthetic thermal oil and two-tank molten salt storage, (ii) molten salt tower plant with direct molten salt storage, and (iii) direct steam tower with steam accumulator storage.

The following main assumptions have been considered for the design of the storage system for the three plants analysed in this study:

- (i) The same electrical gross output is delivered by the plant, and equal to 100 MWe
- (ii) The same storage capacity in terms of discharging hours at equivalent full nominal conditions is assumed in 1h, 2h, 5h, 9h

It is assumed a similar power cycle, at least from operating conditions point of view. The molten salt tower and direct steam power cycle are set up with a subcritical Rankine turbine operating at 540°C and 130 bar. In the case of the direct steam tower, the discharge from steam accumulators ranges from the maximum operating pressure (130 bar) and the minimum working pressure assumed by the turbine which is supposed to be 2 bar. On the other hand, the power cycle working conditions for the parabolic trough plant with synthetic oil and molten salt storage are set up with a subcritical Rankine turbine operating at 380°C and 100 bar (see Table 3).

	Oil Parabolic Trough with Molten Salt TES	Molten Salt Tower with Molten Salt TES	Direct Steam Tower with Steam Accumulator TES
Gross Power [MWe]	100	100	100
Turbine Inlet Steam Pressure [bar]	100	130	120
Turbine Inlet Steam Temperature [°C]	380	550	540
TES hot temperature [°C]	386	565	330
TES cold temperature [°C]	283	288	124

Table 3 Working cycle and TES conditions for the STE plants typology considered within this study

It has been considered 4 cases related to the charging hours in order to analyse the impact of size in the storage total cost. In the case of molten salt thermal energy storage, depending on the salt volume, it has been considered different number of tanks. Table 4 shows the number of molten salt tanks used for each case.

	Oil Parabolic Trough with Molten Salt TES				Molten Salt Tower with Molten Salt TES			
Storage hours	1	2	5	9	1	2	5	9
Number of cold tanks	1	1	2	3	1	1	1	1
Number of hot tanks	1	1	2	3	1	1	1	1

Table 4 Number of molten salt storage tanks considered for each case in the study

For the direct steam storage with steam accumulators, the storage cost will consider the following items: (i) pressure vessel tanks, (ii) foundations, (iii) heat exchanger for superheating, (iv) piping and mechanical erection, and (v) electrical and I&C. Storage medium is not considered as being water, hence negligible from cost point of view.

For molten salt two tank storage, it is considered (i) molten salt storage tanks (which includes the hot storage tanks, cold storage tanks and molten salt pumps, among others), (ii) molten salt

medium inventory, (iii) molten salt melting system, (iv) piping and mechanical erection, (v) electrical and I&C, and (vi) civil works. Insulation and foundation are included in the cost of both hot and cold storage tanks. In the case of the parabolic trough plant the oil-to-salt heat exchanger is included within the equipment item.

Figures 21 to 23 represents the energy cost per item considered for the steam accumulator and molten salt storage systems for each STE plant. The comparison is done for the four cases depending on the discharging hours at full load capacity.

Figure 21 TES energy cost breakdown per item for a direct steam tower of 100 MW with steam accumulator TES (DSGT: Direct Steam Generation Tower)

Figure 22 TES energy cost breakdown per item for an oil parabolic trough plant of 100 MWe with molten salt TES (PTC: Parabolic Trough Collector)

Figure 23 TES energy cost breakdown per item for a molten salt tower of 100 MWe and molten salt TES (MST: Molten Salt Tower)

In the case of steam accumulator TES, the main cost is related to the pressure vessel tanks, reaching values between 60 and 70% of the TES total costs defined as US\$/kWhth. That means, that the larger the thermal capacity is needed, the higher percentage will be.

The cost of storage medium is very important. Lots of research is currently being done to search and develop new solutions to store energy at low cost in order to reduce the LCOE of STE plants. However, with the current molten salts used in the STE industry, it is difficult to get an accurate cost because industrial salts are produced on a regional level and producers compete directly with each other setting the price. In this study, material costs, melting system costs and handling costs have been considered. Considering the molten salt storage system, it can be seen that the storage capacity significantly affects the molten salt inventory increasing its thermal storage energy cost, while the equipment thermal cost reduces going to higher storage capacities. For the oil parabolic trough plant, this increment is even higher because molten salt inventories are much bigger compared to a similar gross power molten salt tower plant. Also the storage tanks item tend to reduce significantly because the number of tanks, pumps, etc, remains more less the same. In the case of the molten salt tower, the cost of storage tanks reaches almost 50% for low storage capacities, reducing up to 40% when having 9 hours storage discharge. No significant changes occur because the number of tanks as well as other equipments, like the molten metal pumps, remains the same. On the other hand, the thermal cost of molten salt inventory increases from almost 10% up to 28% while increasing storage capacity from 1 to 9 hours.

Figure 24 represents a comparative between the energy cost of the different TES cases analyzed in this study. An oil parabolic trough 50 MW plant with 6 hours of storage using a two-tank molten salt TES system has been used as baseline in order to compare the energy cost. In all the three technologies compared in the study, the energy cost decreases when storage capacity increases. Results show that this is more relevant in the case of the TES for molten salt tower, where energy cost can be reduced around 68%, while the TES for parabolic trough and TES for direct steam tower reduce around 41% and 35%, respectively.

Steam accumulators have lower thermal energy costs than molten salt TES for oil parabolic trough plants. However, it is important to mention that thermal-to-electric efficiencies are slightly different between them.

Figure 24 Relative energy cost of the thermal energy storage systems used within this study

The economic value of the TES system is assessed by the Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) calculation. LCOE is commonly used in power generation as an economic performance metric in order to compare cost of electricity among different power generation sources. Lots of studies have been done in the past to compare the LCOE of a complete solar thermal power plant using or not molten salt storage systems [34, 47-62]. However, there are no specific studies related to the thermal energy storage levelized cost of electricity itself. This study is focused on the comparison of the TES LCOE, which cost is determined using the following equation:

$$TES\ LCOE\ \left[\frac{\$}{kWh} \right] = \frac{(TES\ capital\ cost) * (Fixed\ charge\ rate) + TES\ O\&M\ costs}{Net\ electric\ output\ from\ TES}$$

The investment cost relates to the investment of the TES system which includes the items described previously, including material, installation labour, but do not include engineering, procurement, construction management, or indirect costs. The fixed charge rate is an economic factor which converts the capital cost to an equivalent annual expense [34]. For this study a representative value of 10% is used. Annual O&M costs are exclusively the costs for the TES system. In this case, no fuel cost has been considered as there is no back-up storage from a boiler. Lower O&M costs for steam accumulators are considered compared to molten salt storage mainly because the energy consumption of pumping the storage fluid is almost negligible compared to a molten salt pump. Also heat tracing system is not required in steam accumulator thermal energy storage systems neither in pipes nor tanks. This TES O&M cost decreases when storage capacity in terms of discharging hours increases. It has been estimated a TES O&M cost range of 6.0 to 7.2 \$/MWh for the steam accumulator TES system. For the indirect molten salt TES for parabolic trough the range of TES O&M cost has been estimated in 10.5 to 12.6 \$/MWh, while for the

direct molten salt TES for tower the range is between 9.0 to 10.8 \$/MWh. The denominator shows the sum of the real energy produced from the TES system throughout one year.

Figure 25 represents the relative TES Levelized Cost of Electricity for the different cases analyzed in this study. It has been considered a comparison between each case taking as reference an oil parabolic trough 50 MW plant with 6 hours of storage using a two-tank molten salt TES system.

Figure 25 Comparison of Thermal Energy Storage LCOE

According to Figure 25, molten salt storage using a two-tank configuration is economically attractive if the storage system has a minimum size in order to compensate the extra costs of using smaller tanks which also involve higher equipment costs per kWh. In addition, the high cost of the oil-to-salt heat exchanger is penalized for small storage capacities. The TES LCOE reduction for the two-tank molten salt storage system is around 22% and 24%, respectively, for the molten salt tower and the oil parabolic trough plant increasing storage capacity from 2 hours up to 9 hours. In the case of steam accumulators for direct steam tower, this TES LCOE reduction is around 11%. It can be seen that the TES LCOE for steam accumulator thermal energy storage system is higher than molten salt storage systems and mainly due to the higher investment cost required and a lower production from TES. Nevertheless, a higher TES LCOE does not mean that the steam accumulator technology cannot compete with the molten salt storage system. For a complete assessment of the TES system, several parameters need to be taken into consideration to select the best appropriate thermal energy storage system: power and efficiency of the cycle, location of the plant, demand profile and market conditions, storage hours, material costs, integration and operation strategies of the TES system into the power plant, O&M costs, among others.

As commented above, the TES LCOE calculation applied exclusively for the TES system. For a complete assessment of the total LCOE of the plant, there are several parameters that are also involved to select the best appropriate thermal energy storage system: power and efficiency of the cycle, location of the plant, demand profile and market conditions, storage hours, material costs, integration and operation strategies of the TES system into the power plant, O&M costs, among others.

TES capital cost for a molten salt tower contributes around 16% towards the overall plant capital cost and 14% towards the LCOE [63]. In order to become STE more competitive with other

energy sources, a lot of technological advances in thermal energy storage systems are needed to contribute towards cost reduction. Research and development activities are on-going to increase the operating temperature of the power cycle. The US SunShot program considers increase cycle temperature up to 650°C using supercritical cycles that could enable the possibility to increase the solar-to-electricity efficiency as well as reduce thermal storage volumes and by hence, decrease the capital costs and the levelized cost of electricity.

4. Conclusions

This paper presents a technical and economical assessment of the commercial thermal energy storage systems used in solar thermal electricity plants. Cost analysis is conducted to evaluate the economic comparison of the steam accumulator and two-tank molten salt thermal energy storage concepts for each plant configuration.

A two-tank molten salt storage system is considered for the oil parabolic trough case and the direct molten salt tower. Inorganic nitrate salt mixtures are the preferred storage medium due to a favourable combination of thermal and chemical properties. This system is able to supply energy at constant conditions during the discharge, without having big concerns about corrosion phenomena or degradation of salts. However, in the case of a parabolic trough plant, it needs significant time to switch from charging to discharging conditions, not allowing the system as buffer storage or to protect the turbine against transients.

This TES system is the most used thermal storage in solar thermal electricity plants, but its working conditions are limited by the synthetic thermal oil used in the solar field. Thermal degradation in the oil limits the molten salt temperature up to 400°C. In addition, compared to the molten salt tower of direct steam tower, higher numbers of heat exchange equipments are needed to transfer energy to the power block.

Using a molten salt tower, the two-tank system allows increasing the hot temperature up to 565°C, increasing the efficiency of the power cycle as well as reducing the volume per energy stored.

Steam accumulators are considered for direct steam storage. It is a very well-known technology with several years of experience in solar thermal electricity plants and decades in other industries. One of the main advantages is that the storage fluid is water avoiding the uncertainty in the price of the storage medium. Fast reaction times and high discharge rates make steam accumulators a well-proven option for compensation of transients but also as a mid-term storage system to meet supply/demand curves when there is no radiation. Using the volume of components like separator drum or heat exchangers for storage of pressurized hot water is also a cost-effective approach to integrate and increase buffer storage capacity. It also allows to protect the components of power plants from the effects of transients. On the other hand, steam accumulator concept is penalized by the relationship of the volume to the energy stored as well as the discharge process that shows a decline in pressure not reaching nominal conditions in the turbine.

From the economic point of view, the main cost of a steam accumulator TES is related to the pressure vessel tanks, reaching values between 60 and 70% of the TES total thermal costs defined as US\$/kWh_{th}. The possibility of cost reduction is directly related to the cost of the material of pressure vessels which is a market price. It can be seen that for low storage capacities the thermal cost for a steam accumulator TES system is lower than the indirect or direct molten salt storage. This is mainly due to the high cost that both molten salt storage systems have per molten salt volume stored. In addition for the parabolic trough plant, the cost is even higher for a small storage system due to the high cost of heat exchangers.

In the case of the molten salt storage system one of the major cost drivers is the salt medium, where its thermal cost reaches values between 25 to 40%, and 10 to 30%, from 1 to 9 hours for the indirect and direct storage, respectively. It can be seen that the storage capacity affects

significantly the molten salt inventory while the storage tanks thermal cost reduces going from low to higher storage capacities because the number of tanks, pumps, etc, remains more or less the same. For the oil parabolic trough plant, this increment is even higher because molten salt inventories are much bigger compared to a similar gross power molten salt tower plant due to a lower temperature gradient in the salts.

In the case of the direct molten salt storage, the cost of storage tanks reaches almost 50% for low storage capacities, reducing up to 40% when having 9 hours storage discharge. On the other hand, the thermal cost of molten salt inventory increases significantly from almost 10% up to 28% while increasing storage capacity from 1 to 9 hours. The great potential of direct molten salt TES is even more representative for large storage capacities, as the salt inventory volume decreases significantly due to the higher energy density stored compared to the other commercial storage systems. The system is relatively simple and a well understood technology. Not using heat exchangers and the smaller storage size needed for the same capacities due to the bigger temperature gradients are the most important benefits for the direct molten salt storage system.

In all the three technologies compared in the study, the cost decreases when storage capacity increases. Results show that this is more relevant in the case of the TES for molten salt tower, where energy cost can be reduced around 68%, while the TES for direct steam tower and TES for parabolic trough reduce around 35% and 41%, respectively. Steam accumulators have lower thermal energy costs than molten salt TES for oil parabolic trough plants. However, it is important to mention that thermal-to-electric efficiencies are slightly different between them.

All the LCOE estimations done up to date look for obtain the economic benefits of the overall STE plant by using thermal energy storage system to increase dispatchability, capacity factors while reducing the levelized cost of electricity. In this paper, the study is slightly different and searches to compare the LCOE directly related to the thermal energy storage system. For that, capital and O&M cost related to the storage system, as well as the annual production from TES are calculated for each case. The comparison between each case is done taking as reference a 50 MW parabolic trough plant using thermal oil as HTF and a 6 hours storage using a two-tank molten salt TES system. It has been considered a comparison between each case taking as reference an oil parabolic trough 50 MW plant with 6 hours of storage using a two-tank molten salt TES system.

Molten salt storage using a two-tank configuration is economically attractive if the storage system has a minimum size in order to compensate the extra costs of using smaller tanks which involves also higher equipment costs per kWh. The high cost of the oil-to-salt heat exchanger is penalized for small storage capacities in the indirect molten salt storage.

The TES LCOE analysis confirms that the lowest electricity prices are reached with the direct molten salt storage for the whole storage capacity cases. The TES LCOE reduction for the indirect molten salt storage system is around 22% while for the direct molten salt storage rises up to 24% increasing storage capacity from 2 hours up to 9 hours. In the case of steam accumulators for direct steam tower, this TES LCOE reduction is around 11%.

This study confirms that steam accumulator thermal energy storage system represents an attractive option as a buffer instead of large capacity storages facilitating the operation of STE plants protecting the turbine from transients. This benefit is more representative when decreasing the power of the plant where the molten salt storage is even more cost affected, favouring the steam accumulator technology as the best option for lower power and storage capacities. On the other hand, molten salt storage system represents the best option for large storage capacities.

However, for a complete assessment of the total LCOE of the plant, several parameters need to be taken into consideration to select the best appropriate thermal energy storage system: power and efficiency of the cycle, location of the plant, demand profile and market conditions, storage hours, material costs, integration and operation strategies of the TES system into the power plant, O&M costs, among others.

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References

- [1] IEA (International Energy Agency). World Energy Outlook Special Report 2015: Energy and Climate Change - Executive Summary
- [2] WRI (World Resources Institute). Climate Analysis Indicators Tool (CAIT) 2.0: WRI's climate data explorer, 2014. <http://cait.wri.org> Accessed January 2016
- [3] FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization). FAOSTAT: Emissions - land use, 2014. http://faostat3.fao.org/faostat-gateway/go/to/download/G2/*E Accessed January 2016
- [4] IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) Mitigation of Climate Change: Trends in stocks and flows of GHGs and their drivers, 2014. https://www.ipcc.ch/pdf/unfccc/sbsta40/SED/1_blanco_sed3.pdf
- [5] Sirus Mohammadi, Ali Mohammadi. Stochastic scenario-based model and investigating size of battery energy storage and thermal energy storage for micro-grid. International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems 61, October 2014, Pages 531-546.
- [6] IRENA (International Renewable Energy Agency). Thermal Energy Storage Technology Brief. IEA-ETSAP and IRENA Technology Brief E17 - January 2013
- [7] Sarada Kuravi, Jamie Trahan, D. Yogi Goswami, Muhammad M. Rahman, Elias K. Stefanakos. Thermal energy storage technologies and systems for concentrating solar power plants. Progress in Energy and Combustion Science Volume 39, Issue 4, August 2013, Pages 285–319
- [8] Hank Price, Eckhard Lüpfer, David Kearney, Eduardo Zarza, Gilbert Cohen, Randy Gee and Rod Mahoney. Advances in Parabolic trough solar power technology. Journal of Solar Energy Engineering 124(2), 109-125
- [9] Cohen GE. Nevada Solar One update, Proceedings of the third concentrated solar power summit, US, San Francisco, Hotel Nikko, 2008
- [10] Sharon J. Wagner, Edward S. Rubin. Economic implications of thermal energy storage for concentrated solar thermal power. Renewable Energy, Volume 61, January 2014, Pages 81-95
- [11] Hussein Ibrahim and Adrian Ilinca. Techno-Economic Analysis of Different Energy Storage Technologies. 2013
- [12] IRENA (International Renewable Energy Agency). Renewable Energy Technologies: Cost Analysis Series. Volume 1: Power Sector Issue 2/5 Concentrating Solar Power. June 2012
- [13] Haoran Zhao, Qiuwei WuaShuju Huc, Honghua Xu, Claus Nygaard Rasmussen. Review of Energy Storage System for Wind Power Integration Support. Applied Energy, Volume 137, 1 January 2015, Pages 545-553
- [14] D.O. Akinyele, R.K. Rayudu. Review of energy storage technologies for sustainable power networks. Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments, Volume 8, December 2014, Pages 74-91

- [15] Xing Luo, Jihong Wang, Mark Dooner, Jonathan Clarke. Overview of current development in electrical energy storage technologies and the application potential in power system operation. *Applied Energy*, Volume 137, 1 January 2015, Pages 511-536
- [16] <http://solartoday.org/2012/05/thermal-energy-storage-solution/> visited January 17th, 2016
- [17] Pachecho, J.E. and Gilbert, R. Overview of recent results of the Solar Two test and evaluations program. In *Renewable and advanced energy systems for the 21st century* RAES'99-7731. ASME, New York
- [18] Herrmann U, Kearney D.W. Survey of thermal energy storage for parabolic trough power plants. *Journal of Solar Energy Engineering* 2002;124(2): 145e52
- [19] Rainer Tamme. IEA ECES Annex 19. Optimised Industrial Process Heat and Power Generation with Thermal Energy Storage. Final report, July 2010
- [21] Solar Paces website CSP technology description <http://www.solarpaces.org/csp-technology> visited January 26th, 2016
- [21] <http://energy.gov/eere/energybasics/articles/linear-concentrator-system-basics-concentrating-solar-power> visited January 22nd, 2016
- [22] Fichtner. Technology Assessment of CSP Technologies for a Site Specific Project in South Africa Final Report, The World Bank and ESMAP, Washington D.C. 2010
- [23] National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) project listing <http://www.nrel.gov/csp/solarpaces/> visited January 19th, 2016
- [24] CSP World website <http://www.cspworld.org/cspworldmap> visited January 17th, 2016
- [25] Ming Liu, N.H. Steven Tay, Stuart Bell, Martin Belusko, Rhys Jacob, Geoffrey Will, Wasim Saman, Frank Bruno. Review on concentrating solar power plants and new developments in high temperature thermal energy storage technologies. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. Volume 53, January 2016, Pages 1411–1432.
- [26] Divya KC, Østergaard J. Battery energy storage technology for power systems —an overview. *ElectrPowerSystRes*2009;79:511–20
- [27] Pankaj K. Choubey, Min-seuk Kim, Rajiv R. Srivastava, Jae-chun Lee, Jin-Young Lee. Advance review on the exploitation of the prominent energy-storage element - Lithium. Part I - From mineral and brine resources. *Minerals Engineering*, Volume 89, April 2016, Pages 119-137
- [28] U.S.Department of Energy. 2014 SunShot initiative portfolio book: concentrating solar power. Washington, DC: Office of Energy Efficiency & Renewable Energy, U.S. Department of Energy; 2014
- [29] Sioshansi R, Denholm P. The value of concentrating solar power and thermal energy storage. NREL-TP-6A2-45833 2010
- [30] Reilly HE, Kolb WJ. Evaluation of molten salt power tower technology based on the experience of solar two. SAND2001-3674. Sandia National Laboratories; 2001
- [31] Kearney D, Kelly B, Cable R, et al. Evaluation of a molten salt heat transfer fluid in a parabolic trough solar field. *Int Sol Energ Conf* 2002;293–9
- [32] Kearney D, Kelly B, Herrmann U, et al. Engineering aspects of a molten salt heat transfer fluid in a trough solar field. *Energy* 2004;29:861–70
- [33] Winter C, Sizmann R, Vant-Hull L. Solar power plants. Chapter 6: Thermal storage for solar power plants. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg 1991
- [34] Ulf Herrmann, Bruce Kelly, Henry Price “Two-Tank Molten Salt Storage for Parabolic Trough Solar Power Plants” 2004

- [35] Herrmann U, Geyer M, Kearney D. Overview on thermal storage systems. Workshop on Thermal Storage for Trough Power Plants. FLABEG Solar International GmbH; 2006
- [36] Kelly B, Kearney D. Thermal storage commercial plant design study for a 2-tank indirect molten salt system. National Renewable Energy Laboratory; 2004. NREL/SR-550-40166
- [37] Tyner C, Kolb G, Prairie M, Weinrebe G, Valverde A, Sanchez E. Solar power tower development: recent experiences. SAND96-2662C 1993
- [38] Gregory J. Kolb “An Evaluation of Possible Next-Generation High Temperature Molten-Salt Power Towers”. SAND2011-9320
- [39] Informe Anual PSA 2006
- [40] Beckmann, G., Gilli, P.V., 1984. Thermal Energy Storage. Springer-Verlag, Berlin
- [41] Report for NNE5-1999-356 (5th Framework Programme) Contract with the European Commission (PS10 Final Report)
- [42] Goldstern, W., 1970. Steam Storage Installation. Pergamon Press, Oxford
- [43] Wolf-Dieter Steinmann, Markus Eck. Buffer storage for direct steam generation. Solar Energy, Volume 80, Issue 10, October 2006, Pages 1277-1282
- [44] Goldstern, Walter “Steam storage installations”. Springer-Verlag OHG, Berlin / Göttingen / Heidelberg, 1970
- [45] <http://www2.spiraxsarco.com/> visited January 22nd, 2016
- [46] Pacheco J.E., Gilbert R., “Overview of Recent Results of the Solar Two Test and Evaluations Program”, Renewable and Advanced Energy Systems for the 21st Century, Proceedings of the 1999 ASME International Solar Energy Conference, Maui, HI, April 11-14, 1999
- [47] B. Kelly, D. Kearney. Thermal storage commercial plant design study for a 2-tank indirect molten salt system. Final Report May13, 2002 – December 31, 2004. Subcontract Report NREL/SR-550-40166 July 2006
- [48] Craig Turchi, Mark Mehos, Clifford K. Ho and Gregory J. Kolb. Current and future costs for parabolic trough and power tower systems in the US market. Conference Paper NREL/CP-5500-49303. October 2010
- [49] Sargent & Lundy LLC Consulting Group. Assessment of Parabolic Trough and Power Tower Solar Technology Cost and Performance Forecasts. NREL/SR-550-34440. October 2003
- [50] D. Kearney, U. Herrmann, P. Nava, B. Kelly, R. Mahoney, J. Pacheco, R. Cable, N. Potrovitza, D. Blake and H. Price. Assessment of a molten salt heat transfer fluid in a parabolic trough solar field. Journal of Solar Energy Engineering Volume 125 Issue 2 Pages 170-176. 2003
- [51] Gregory J. Kolb, Clifford K. Ho, Thomas R. Mancini, and Jesse A. Gary. Power tower technology roadmap and cost reduction plan. Sandia Report SAND2011-2419. April 2011
- [52] Gregory J. Kolb. An evaluation of possible next-generation high-temperature molten-salt power towers. Sandia Report SAND2011-9320. December 2011
- [53] C. Parrado, A. Marzo, E. Fuentealba, A.G. Fernández. 2050 LCOE improvement using new molten salts for thermal energy storage in CSP plants. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, Volume 57, May 2016, Pages 505-514
- [54] Ben Xu, Peiwen Li, Cholik Chan. Application of phase change materials for thermal energy storage in concentrated solar thermal power plants: A review to recent developments. Applied Energy, Volume 160, 15 December 2015, Pages 286-307

- [55] T. Richert, K. Riffelmann, P. Nava. The Influence of Solar Field Inlet and Outlet Temperature on the Cost of Electricity in a Molten Salt Parabolic Trough Power Plant. *Energy Procedia*, Volume 69, May 2015, Pages 1143-1151
- [56] M.J. Montes, A. Abánades, J.M. Martínez-Val. Performance of a direct steam generation solar thermal power plant for electricity production as a function of the solar multiple. *Solar Energy*, Volume 83, Issue 5, May 2009, Pages 679-689
- [57] Fabrizio De Luca, Vittorio Ferraro, Valerio Marinelli. On the performance of CSP oil-cooled plants, with and without heat storage in tanks of molten salts. *Energy*, Volume 83, 1 April 2015, Pages 230-239
- [58] Antonio L. Avila-Marin, Jesus Fernandez-Reche, Felix M. Tellez. Evaluation of the potential of central receiver solar power plants: Configuration, optimization and trends. *Applied Energy*, Volume 112, December 2013, Pages 274-288
- [59] Sharon J. Wagner, Edward S. Rubin. Economic implications of thermal energy storage for concentrated solar thermal power. *Renewable Energy*, Volume 61, January 2014, Pages 81-95
- [60] J. Hernández-Moro, J.M. Martínez-Duart. CSP electricity cost evolution and grid parities based on the IEA roadmaps. *Energy Policy*, Volume 41, February 2012, Pages 184-192
- [61] Jan Fabian Feldhoff, Kai Schmitz, Markus Eck, Lars Schnatbaum-Laumann, Doerte Laing, Francisco Ortiz-Vives, Jan Schulte-Fischedick. Comparative system analysis of direct steam generation and synthetic oil parabolic trough power plants with integrated thermal storage. *Solar Energy*, Volume 86, Issue 1, January 2012, Pages 520-530
- [62] M. Moser, F. Trieb, T. Fichter, J. Kern, H. Maier, P. Schicktanz. Techno-economic Analysis of Enhanced Dry Cooling for CSP. *Energy Procedia*, Volume 49, 2014, Pages 1177-1186
- [63] Christine SMITH, Yanping SUN, Brian WEBBY , Andrew BEATH and Frank BRUNO, "Cost analysis of high temperature thermal energy storage for solar power plant" - Proceedings of the 52nd Annual Conference, Australian Solar Energy Society (Australian Solar Council) Melbourne May 2014 ISBN: 948-0-646-92219-5